

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION BY FORMING CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS

Matkarimova Mukaddas Komilovna

Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of CHDPU

I-course graduate student

matkarimovamukaddas2@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10947213>

ANNOTATION

This article provides information on the development of creativity skills of secondary school students in English classes and interactive methods that develop creativity during class activities.

This article provides information on the development of creativity in the English language classes of secondary school students and interactive methods that develop creativity skills during the lessons.

Key words: creativity, interactive methods, innovation, motivation, creative emotion, intellect, didactic.

Ключевые слова: творчество, интерактивные методы, инновации, мотивация, творческая эмоция, интеллект, дидактика.

In a situation where the pace of development in all fields is accelerating in the world, teaching the young generation based on new creative approaches - improving the quality of education is one of the urgent tasks in the field. In particular, bringing the quality of education to a new level in general education schools, which are the first link and foundation of education, has become the need of the hour today. Therefore, pedagogues should educate the young generation, especially schoolchildren, in such a way that they can compete with the students of the developed countries of the world, who can respond to the demands of the rapidly developing era, are independent, creative, and think critically. The rapid development of the era shows the need to make a radical change in the field of education, to provide quality education to today's young generation using modern technologies and interactive methods.

Providing high-quality education directly depends on educational and methodological support, because the role of educational literature is great in mastering each subject, in gaining a general idea and knowledge about the subject. For this reason, it is necessary to set the requirements for educational literature created for each type of education, such as developing creative thinking, psychological-pedagogical, methodological-didactic, continuous education and critical thinking.

Active methods of education not only help to encourage students to think actively and do practical activities during the learning process, but also help to form positive teaching motivation, reveal and develop creative abilities, and help to master the learning material with high efficiency will give. In recent years, the number of people of different ages learning English in our country is increasing day by day. Because, in today's rapidly developing era, it is becoming more and more difficult to live without understanding the English language. It should be remembered that language learning is also related to the youth period. Secondary school students learn foreign languages from the first grade, and the knowledge acquired at

such a young age will definitely pay off in the future, and not only the students but also the teachers are required to perform as well as expected. It is appropriate to give tasks that develop creativity during the lessons. It is possible to see the development of students' knowledge through the use of creative, interactive methods that are effective not only for the teacher, but also for students for each stage of the English language classes.

In particular, starting the English lessons with "Warm-up" exercises, mainly songs in English, videos and slides related to the topic will help to bring students from other subjects to the English language environment. "Icebreaker" method, "Who am I?" Methods such as "Play the Number Game" can be effectively used in lesson processes. , the use of multimedia tools and Internet resources with the help of a computer greatly contributes to the development of students' listening comprehension, oral speech, writing and speaking skills, and the development of students' creative thinking, requires a lot of skill. The creative game methods shown above for the development of oral speech show good results. Therefore, if we take the "Icebreaker" method, the teacher first says his name, and the audience continues. Before saying his name, the student should repeat the names listed before him. This method is especially helpful in establishing cordial and friendly relations with new teachers and students, and improves their attention and memory. In the "Chain Drill" game method, students quickly say new words related to the topic one after the other, trying not to break the chain. This process also helps students to pay attention and remember the words. Using different music and songs and dialogues for students to listen and understand well helps to increase knowledge and efficiency. As a result of memorizing songs, students' ability to know words and lexical units increases. When creating dialogues, their creative abilities, logical and critical thinking also develop. "Who am I?" that is, "Who am I?" In the game method, the names of famous people are written on several cards and turned upside down. A student chooses one of them and passes it to the teacher without reading it. At this point, that student looks upside down at the board and asks, "Who am I?" asks, and the rest describe famous people in English. The student must find which famous person's name is written on the card. In this process, they develop such characteristics as creative thinking, resourcefulness, and a broad outlook. "Draw a picture" game method is very useful for learning words related to the members of body. In this game method, the names of body parts are written on the board in English. Head, hair, ears, face, lips, teeth, hand, neck and etc.

Each student writes his name on a separate piece of paper and folds that part so that it is not visible and replaces it. The teacher reads and shows the member written on the board. Pupils write it down on paper. After each member, they change paper and draw a picture of a person. At the end of the game, the names are revealed and everyone sees their picture. Through this method of the game, students' listening comprehension skills and abilities, creative imagination develop. In order to meet the requirements of the curriculum, it is recommended to have a computer or electronic board in every English classroom. Today, it is very important to form the four skills that are important in language learning can be effectively applied and, as a result, positive learning and creative development of students can be observed.

In particular, project work, independent work, working in groups and pairs are among the methods that develop students' creative abilities. Their ability to deal with each other, their knowledge of the subject, their intellect and creativity are demonstrated. For example, when preparing a flowchart for students of the 6th grade on the topic of "Environment" in the

Unit-6 "Environment" section, students are divided into small groups, and they will learn how people recycle paper, plastic, or aluminum. They will search for information about the possibilities and prepare a creative flow chart based on the information they have collected. The group members will have to make a presentation on the flow chart together, and such tasks will increase their creativity, that each item should be used sparingly, and in the future encourages students to find modern and creative ways to recycle these waste products. To use this game exercise, you can choose from a variety of topics covered. For example, if the topic is "Helping the environment", first tell the students where such boxes are (restaurants, offices, companies) and people in the boxes. It is explained that they write down their suggestions without writing their names. The sentences prepared by the teacher are glued to the side that is considered correct by the students, and the direction of thinking is explained. For example. A correct sign is placed on one side, and an incorrect sign is placed on the other side.

We shouldn't use a lot of electricity and gas.

We should use wind and solar power.

We need to use more wind and solar power.

In this game exercise, students use the verb should to give recommendations, look for ways to help the environment and try to find a creative solution to it.

The ability of schoolchildren to combine their previous knowledge with newly learned knowledge while solving various tasks in the English language prepares students for life and teaches them to find solutions in various problem situations. Creativity in order to form the character, a creative environment should be created by the teacher in the course of the lesson. Analyzing and explaining the specific solutions of each given creative assignment with the students will lead to a good result of the project work and the development of their creative abilities.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947//Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017., No. 6, Article 70.
2. Guilford J.P. (Creativity, American Psychologist, Volume 5, Issue 9, 444-454.
3. Ibragimova G.N. Development of creative abilities of students based on interactive teaching methods and technologies.
4. Lucy Frino "Guess what!" Teacher's book 6./Teacher's book.- Cambridge University Press., 2022.-B.71
5. Jo'rayev, S., & Abdurasulov, J. (2024). SUBJECT, TASKS AND CONTENT OF STUDYING THE BASICS OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION. В АCADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 7, сс. 149–153). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10700581>
6. Jurayev, S., & Abdurasulov, J. (2024). PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF A MILITARY OFFICER. International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science, 2(1), 26–29. Retrieved from <https://aidlix.org/index.php/fi/article/view/547>
7. Abdurasulov J. (2024). HARBIY PEDAGOGIKANING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN ALOQASI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 48–52. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28164>

8.Matkarimova , M. . (2024). O'QUVCHILARGA KREATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA INGLIZ TILI O'QITISHNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 46-47. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28163>

